

6G-BRICKS: Building Reusable testbed Infrastructures for Cloud-to-device breakthrough technologies

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Abstract—Sixth generation (6G)-enabled massive network MANO orchestration, alongside distributed supervision and fully reconfigurable control logic that manages dynamic arrangement of network components, such as cell-free, Open-Air Interface (OAI) and RIS, is a potent enabler for the upcoming pervasive digitalization of the vertical use cases. In such a disruptive domain, artificial intelligence (AI)-driven zero-touch “Network of Networks” intent-based automation shall be able to guarantee a high degree of security, efficiency, scalability, and sustainability, especially in cross-domain and interoperable deployment environments (i.e., where points of presence (PoPs) are non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID)). To this extent, this paper presents a novel breakthrough, open, and fully reconfigurable networking architecture for 6G cellular paradigms, named 6G-BRICKS. To this end, 6G-BRICKS will deliver the first open and programmable O-RAN Radio Unit (RU) for 6G networks, termed as the OpenRU, based on an NI USRP-based platform. Moreover, 6G-BRICKS will integrate the RIS concept into the OAI alongside Testing as a Service (TaaS) capabilities, multi-tenancy, disaggregated Operations Support Systems (OSS) and Deep Edge adaptation at the forefront. The overall ambition of 6G-BRICKS is to offer evolvability, granularity, while, at the same time, tackling big challenges such as interdisciplinary efforts and big investments in 6G integration.

Keywords—6G, AI-enabled network orchestration, XAI, B5G, Cell-Free (CF), CF massive MIMO (CFmMIMO), MIMO, O-RAN, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), xApp, network testbeds

I. INTRODUCTION

Commercial deployments of 5G are now progressing worldwide, delivering new capabilities, improved performance and new applications for customers. For Mobile Network Operators, a set of features that are supported 5G, including network slicing, disaggregation, and cloud-native design, are enabling the use of new applications and new business models. The gradual shift to the full digitization of the real world is expected to create vast amounts of generated data and applications, like immersive communication, and holographic telepresence, while social experiences powered by Extended Reality (XR) will become our default way of communication in the near future. These emerging applications exceed the current and future capabilities of 5G networks, both in terms of KPIs that must be supported, and in terms of their requirements on an ultra-dense computational infrastructure, to support the required degree of computational offloading [1]. Thus, academia and industry have shifted their attention to the investigation of a new generation of Smart Networks capable of supporting such performance. The first results of these studies show that 6G networks will deliver efficiency clearly superior to 5G and satisfy evolving services and applications, making them a key enabler for the intelligent digital society of 2030. Several breakthrough ideas have been already proposed for 6G like joint communication and sensing, cell-free, Radio Intelligent Surfaces, complete cloud continuum etc. [2].

The European Commission innovated via the 5G-PPP program, and supported large scale experimental facilities to facilitate synergies in the whole community of industries, including SMEs, and academia. But to win this race towards shaping the next-generation communication ecosystem, it is clear that a new generation of testbed infrastructures and breakthrough ideas are needed. Inside the framework of Horizon 2020 calls - ICT-20 5G Long Term Evolution and ICT-52 Smart Connectivity beyond 5G, the need of pioneer research projects and innovations streams for key 6g technologies is of paramount importance. Towards this aim, 6G-BRICKS will be the first open 6G platform that combines cell-free, Open-Air Interface (OAI) and RIS and it while adopting will leverage the proven principles of softwarization, open Interfaces (O-RAN), and Open-Source software stacks, putting future expansion and evolvability at its core. However, experience from past 5G-PPP efforts has shown that the enormous complexity of the standards and software stacks makes evolvability and scaling-out efforts extremely challenging, requiring interdisciplinary efforts and big investments in integration.

This is where 6G-BRICKS steps in, bringing together specialists on breakthrough 6G technologies, such as cell-free networking, distributed processing, and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), and adopting principles of *modularity* and *softwarization* to deliver the first truly modular end-to-end 6G experimentation platform in Europe. 6G-BRICKS will structure the various architecture tiers around the concept of “LEGO Bricks” [10], delivering self-contained testbed nodes that can be reused across testbed infrastructures. This significantly lowers the barrier of entry to an end-to-end experimentation platform for specialists to bring their breakthrough technologies for validation and experimentation.

6G-BRICKS will adopt the trend of Software-Defined Infrastructures (SDI) and Software Networks that replace “black boxes” (e.g., physical network functions, such as firewalls) with their softwarized equivalents. This trend will be extended to the RAN via the O-RAN initiative, aiming to evolve O-RAN elements in the 6G era via the integration of breakthrough technologies. To this end, 6G-BRICKS will deliver the first open and programmable O-RAN Radio Unit (RU) for 6G networks, termed as the OpenRU, based on an NI USRP-based platform. Moreover, 6G-BRICKS will integrate the RIS concept into the OAI. In addition, 6G-BRICKS will deliver breakthrough experimentation tools, going well beyond the current Testing as a Service (TaaS) capabilities of current initiatives, and allowing experiments also on devices via O-RAN compliant xAPPs. Thus, the 6G-BRICKS facility aims to serve a dual role, both as a playground for testing of advanced vertical applications and for validation testing and showcasing of the clear benefits and capabilities of 6G breakthrough technologies and devices. Moreover, it will deliver and test new architecture principles, with multi-tenancy, disaggregated Operations Support Systems (OSS) and Deep Edge integration at the forefront.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II depicts the major innovation areas that are promising as part of the overall ambition of 6G-BRICKS, as well as the primary challenges that 6G-BRICKS will address and the novel concepts that it will develop. The next Section, Section III illustrates the

conceptual architectural diagram of the framework alongside the brief description of its core components. Section IV demonstrates the state-of-the-art of 6G use cases that will benefit from the project technicalities. Finally, Section V concludes this research aim.

II. 6G-BRICKS AMBITION

6G networks are expected to adopt a federated, extended edge, with Deep Edge devices integrated into micro-service chains in a cloud-to-device computing continuum. This allows for dynamic deployment, instantiation, migration, or scaling of cloud-native service chains across devices and domains. 6G-BRICKS will support Deep Edge integration through the innovative UE Farm concept and Near Edge integration through a disaggregated wireless X-Haul solution by ICOM. This next-generation telecommunication system offers cost savings, innovation acceleration, quick feature deployment, and ecosystem openness. The disaggregated X-Haul will serve as an additional MEC hosting platform for optimized deployment of 6G-BRICKS cloud native applications. The following are, perhaps, the most profound innovation concepts 6G-BRICKS will introduce as part of mitigating several hardcore challenges in the 6G arena.

A. Innovation Area 1: Intelligent management of the Extended Edge Continuum

6G-BRICKS is a resource management and abstraction framework called PaaS, compliant with ETSI NFV IFA 029 specifications, that offers heterogeneous Extended Edge and cloud infrastructures. The framework includes a mediation framework built around a layered IoT platform, such as EdgeX Foundry, to create adaptive and dynamic environments and enable secure and interoperable resource and service sharing through open APIs. The π -edge platform is employed to support self-synthesized federated infrastructures, optimizing resource/energy efficiency, minimizing deployment speed, and incorporating self-healing/self-learning capabilities for automated infrastructure resilience. The PaaS framework facilitates the automated deployment and auto-provisioning of multi-VM Kubernetes clusters at the device-to-cloud continuum, while implementing elasticity rules to scale clusters based on resource demand. The platform will extend the π -edge platform in an autonomic VIM entity deployable at Near Edge Devices and Deep Edge devices, self-managing the lifecycle of edge resources, and exposing PaaS capabilities for edge service provision.

Fig. 1. PaaS resource management and abstraction framework.

PaaS services are exposed via common and open APIs and can be invoked and utilized by the corresponding Deep Edge DMO [6], [22] – [23]. The Edge DMO can request the deployment of registered PaaS services, and the π -edge platform takes over translating requests to specific runtime configurations, establishing inter-domain links across edge nodes and devices, and maintaining a "working", "secure," and "efficient" state of PaaS services.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the cloudification trend is meant to continue for 6G driving disruptive network design sophistications. The key challenge is to prototype a future 6G network architecture that can fully exploit and interoperate with the cloud platform, as well as grant a fully autonomous End-to-end (E2E) cloud-edge architecture. Security, Privacy, and Trust challenges in the 6G E2E continuum coexist; Security and trustworthiness guarantees require the definition of different levels of abstraction to accommodate the complex interactions across the cloud continuum to be tolerated and risks mitigated. Therefore, there is the need to identify and deliver efficient, secure zero-knowledge trust services between edge and clouds, to allow the integration of a wealth of data from devices traditionally seen as insecure. Therefore, as a security solution objective for 6G-BRICKS is to increase the zero-knowledge and trust based on cyber threat intelligence, intelligent identity management, trustworthy and sovereign data service interoperability across the continuum.

Fig. 2. The concept of “Device-Edge-Cloud Continuum Orchestration” in 6G networks.

B. Innovation Area 2: Secure inter-domain interconnection and Trust establishment

Inter-domain security is crucial for next-generation networks, as they enable ubiquitous computing and networking concepts. 6G-BRICKS provides a unique 2-tiered end-to-end security solution, combining VPN-as-a-Service for cross-testbed connectivity and a Zero-Trust solution for authorization. The GEANT network offers cross-site VPN encrypted tunnels, while SecaaS provides personalized security as a service on-demand. The Security Orchestrator manages security features per service basis, ensuring dynamic provisioning of end-to-end security functions and policy reinforcement across multiple domains, as per NFV-SEC 013 and ETSI NFV-SEC 024 standards.

C. Innovation Area 3: Trust establishment via Software Defined Perimeters

Zero-Trust security is a concept in enterprise security that minimizes uncertainty by enforcing a least privilege per-request access rationale. 6G-BRICKS will adopt the Software-Defined Perimeter (SDP) paradigm to implement Zero-Trust, aligning with virtualized components with open interfaces like O-RAN compliant CUs and DUs deployed at edge data centers at 6G

Sites. This approach significantly increases security and containment of security breaches. The 6G-BRICKS will integrate an open-source SDP stack from Waverley Labs, focusing on protecting O-RAN APIs, connecting the RIC controller with Edge sites, and management plane APIs. The NGFW will be deployed at all ingress points, filtering all incoming packets, and an SDP Gateway agent will be deployed behind the NGFW. Perimeters will be dynamically defined, allowing fine-grained access control as defined by the security policy. Resources inside the perimeter are invisible to unauthenticated third parties, reducing attack surface and containing lateral movement when breaches do occur [7] – [9].

D. Innovation Area 4: Unified Domain Management via Explainable AI and Machine Reasoning

The 3GPPP 5G standards have limitations in centralized management of network slices and vertical applications, governed by the OSS/BSS layer. 6G-BRICKS aims to create a new decentralized Management Plane, building on previous distributed orchestration research initiatives like MonB5G. This approach aims to achieve automation and Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) in multi-tenant/multi-stakeholder ecosystems. The 6G-BRICKS DMO proposes a unified framework of Domain Managers and Orchestrators (DMOs) responsible for policy translation and unification via Explainable AI (XAI) mechanisms. The DMO extends the MonB5G Decision Engine (DE) into an explainable DE (XAI-DE) and incorporates Machine Reasoning (MR) models [3] – [5].

The 6G-BRICKS DMO supports a pluggable framework of domain-specific Explainable AI (XAI) models that undertake policy translation at infrastructure domain actions. In cases of inability to meet policy, a root cause analysis is performed, and feedback is returned to the experimenter. The 6G-BRICKS DMO also develops complex ML models supporting explainability, delivering explainable RNN and time series-based models for the first time in the application domain of Compute and Network infrastructures. MR usage towards zero-touch management is demonstrated, with MR modules using the outputs from XAI models to execute root cause analysis and derive possible solutions. The Diagnostic Maker module is re-

Fig. 3. 6G-BRICKS XAI Decision Engine components.

sponsible for the root cause analysis process, considering intent as the basis for starting the analysis. We can show all the above in Figure 3.

E. Innovation Area 5: Distributed Cell-Free breakthrough technologies for 6G Networks

Cell-free networking is essential for Beyond 5G RANs, providing spectral efficiency and performance without interference. However, CPU scalability constraints pose challenges in practical deployments. 6G-BRICKS consortium members are working on distributed cell-free networks, focusing on multi-band and distributed cell-free. The innovations will focus on channel estimation, clustering, and processing, with the main innovation being real-time validation of these functions as software Bricks on cmWave and mmWave USRPs.

Over-the-air (OTA) sync of frequency and phase will be performed in distributed cell-free for the first time. Novel software implementations for mmWave and multi-band systems will be contributed. The challenge is to synergistically instantiate multiple bands serving the same UE, sharing the same fronthaul, and experiencing the same environment. 6G-BRICKS will create multi-band datasets for comparing statistics of adjacent and distinct frequency ranges, enabling the study of multi-band channel estimation, clustering, synchronization, and distributed processing methods.

F. Innovation Area 6: Support of multi-band and mmWave innovations and breakthrough technologies

6G-BRICKS is focusing on multi-band processing to reduce hardware components in the RAN and enable mmWave and cmWave CF by utilizing a sub6-GHz link to provide large-scale information about UEs. This innovation benefits CmWave deployments by sharing statistical averages between DUs, reducing front-haul costs, cluster formation, blocking, and channel estimation overhead. Fronthauling is crucial for high throughput via CF mmWave systems, and 6G-BRICKS will maximize the use of statistics learned in different bands, such as path loss, doppler spreading, and shadowing. The multi-band approach will base cluster formation on large-scale information from measurements in different frequency bands, handling potential blocking scenarios and accounting for future and current blocking. Channel estimation in mmWave bands is another costly operation, but 6G-BRICKS will exploit statistical averages from adjacent bands to compute channel estimates in targeted bands, shortening complex operations and enabling system implementers to deploy CF mmWave systems on cheaper hardware, increasing industrial interest in this groundbreaking technology.

G. Innovation Area 7: CFmMIMO building blocks for precoding, channel estimation, synchronization, and distributed computing

6G-BRICKS aims to make advanced theoretical concepts like scalable CF, distributed computing, synchronization, and channel estimation available as 6G building blocks for validation and integration with industry initiatives [20] – [21]. The project will develop novel channel estimation methods that minimize fronthaul signaling, computational complexity, and errors on the estimated channel. It will focus on estimating

which shared information provides the largest performance enhancement and combine this approach with a multi-band approach for state-of-the-art channel estimation in 6G RAN deployment. The project will explore over-the-air synchronization for distributed CF networks, overcoming scalability and infrastructure challenges. Fronthaul-aware precoding/decoding will be integrated into a full-fledged end-to-end RAN, identifying which other functions in the network impact these schemes.

H. Innovation Area 8: 6G-BRICKS RIS platform design and envisioned components, communication, and sensing

The 6G-BRICKS project aims to integrate RIS with gNB for communication and sensing using a network-controlled model. The RIS control xApp will configure the RIS for both communication and sensing, managing conflicts between data communication and environmental sensing. The project uses OpenAirInterface (OAI) for gNB and the CEA RIS element, with the gNB running on a COTS machine. The signal is sent to a Software Defined Radio (SDR) element, with a Main Hub Unit (MHU) from Interdigital controlled through the USRP using GPIO. The 6G-BRICKS platform will be the first RIS platform open for experimentation, focusing on indoor scenarios like industry 4.0 premises.

The platform will rely on open RAN components, following O-RAN specifications. The RIS is deployed as a standalone element, providing an API for network-assisted or network-controlled RIS models [12] – [19]. The project proposes a novel RIS Control Protocol (RCP) protocol between the RIS reflector and the RIS agent hosted at the gNB, abstracting the RCP protocol to the xApp and experimenter. Figure 4 illustrates the envisioned O-RAN-aligned architecture. We envision a gNB that can run in monolithic or in disaggregated mode. The RIS is deployed as a standalone element providing an API to be controlled by the networks allowing the implementation of a network-assisted or network-controlled RIS model. Aiming at opening the platform for third-party scenario experimentation, we propose integrating the RIS control algorithm as a xApp that runs on top of the RIC Near-time controller. Therefore, experimenters can, for instance, upload their RIS control algorithms directly and test its performances using the 6G-BRICKS RIS platform. Finally, we propose a novel RIS Control Protocol (RCP) protocol between the RIS reflector and the RIS agent hosted at the gNB. The role of the latter is to abstract the RCP protocol to the xApp and hence to experimenter.

Fig. 4. Envisioned ISAC model using RIS.

III. CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE

6G-BRICKS is a 6G Experimentation Facility federating Belgium and France's 5G-PPP initiatives, offering Public Cloud and experimentation services. It is accessible to third-party consortiums, vertical application owners, and industry experimenters. The facility features a disaggregated Management Plane and Operations Support System for extensibility, evolvability, and multi-tenancy [24]. The 6G experimentation facility architecture is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. 6G-BRICKS General Architecture

More specifically, the 6G-BRICKS facility will include the following architectural tiers:

- The Core Tier serves as the facility's entry point, offering Public Cloud services to 6G Sites. It deploys mature frontend elements and experimentation engines, delivering DevOps Driven Testing as a Service functionality. A Near-RT RIC testing tool is also delivered, providing low-level RRM and RAN slicing capabilities [25]. The Core Site also offers Business Support System services.
- A disaggregated Management Plane (DMP) consists of Domain Manager Orchestrators (DMOs) for Cloud, Edge, and Network orchestration domains. The DMO layer enforces state-to-action mappings, generates service objectives, and implements them by infrastructure domains. It uses explainable AI mechanisms for policy translation and unification, supports end-to-end slicing, and facilitates loose coupling with the Business Layer.
- The 6G Experimentation Platforms layer integrates 6G technologies in reusable modules with O-RAN interfaces for openness and reusability. The KUL site delivers a Distributed Cell-Free RAN, while the EUR site builds on 5G-EVE and EUR OpenAirInterface O-RAN stacks. UE Farms, managed constellations of devices, support virtualization and service placement at the device level.

The 6G-BRICKS DevOps Environment at ISI/Athena will enhance 5GMediaHUB ICT-41 project, improve TaaS module, and support open calls, validation tools, and Backend Engines.

IV. USE CASE APPLICATIONS

6G-BRICKS technological innovation and advanced abilities described before will become a key driver for enabling several disruptive 6G technologies, enlisted below:

A. Use case 1: Metaverse as an enabler of a Modern Workplace

The Metaverse is an emerging use case that is expected to drive the transition to B5G systems, requiring KPI improvements by at least an order of magnitude. It leverages the latest advances in XR/VR technologies to support social interactions in virtual spaces, aligning with the ongoing digitalization of societies and businesses. Videoconferencing is a key aspect of digital transformation, and disruptive technologies can make it even more compelling, helping mitigate limitations in social interaction. Untethered VR is already at the limit of 5G network capabilities, requiring high downlink capacity and low latency. The Metaverse pushes the limits by allowing users to interact in 360 XR environments while freely navigating in a Virtual Environment (VE).

Recent advancements in the volumetric video domain allow for real-time capture of user volume and inserting holograms into VEs, enabling multiple users to be co-presented in a 3D space while embodied in their self-representation. This UC will demonstrate how network densification via distributed cell-free can make untethered Metaverse UCs a reality, offering acceptable quality of experience and immersive social interactions. Both scenarios adopt the Multi-point Control Unit (MCU) element, which handles real-time processing of "holograms" and ensuring synchronization aspects and state consistency of the VE. The MCU receives and transmits multiple MPEG 3D video streams with volumetric videos, decoding and processing incoming videos into a fused volumetric video for the scene, providing a single stream to client devices.

Fig. 6. Metaverse reality

B. Use case 2: 6G applications for Industry 4.0

The 6G-BRICKS Use Case highlights Industry 4.0 applications and how 6G enablers can improve efficiency by leveraging autonomous robots, digital twinning, and XR. These technologies enable high-volume data collection with low latency, enabling data storage, collection, processing, training, and modeling in centralized and distributed architectures. NGMN considers autonomous robots and enhanced Machine

Communication as key 6G use-cases, reflecting the growth in collaborative robotics and autonomous machines. Autonomous robots can efficiently perform repetitive tasks without human assistance, ensuring continuous production and preventing injury. However, some factories have NLoS issues from mmwave-powered gNBs, which can disrupt connectivity and cause damage. The PoC-1 of this use case showcases how 6G can support autonomous robots for Industry 4.0 by enabling low latency communication and synchronization between robots and remote controllers.

Fig. 7. Industry 4.0 IoT

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a hierarchical network management framework for testbed infrastructures (6G-BRICKS) that adopts a fully distributed, modular, and zero autonomous (with minimal human intervention) AI-as-a-Service and Monitoring-as-a-Service technological concepts to reconfigure, provision and orchestrate disarranged RAN components, virtual network functions, AI agents and core applications inside the 6G paradigm. Furthermore, secure AI/ML framework entities for Explainable AI (XAI) comprise the 6G-BRICKS architecture. Finally, 6G-BRICKS fulfils its soft actor-critic based algorithms with great efficiency, alongside an energy-friendly, and ecology sustainable manner. Two innovative use-case scenarios are also being elaborated. However, some research challenges are also mentioned in this paper that require further research effort in that direction and are meant to be released as future project research work.

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